

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic Interactions and Taxon Names Found within SternerLab/SternerLab-MammalVirusData hash://md5/dba4a27432ae3366d8e22c6c13c3c4fc

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named SternerLab/SternerLab-MammalVirusData, has fingerprint hash://md5/dba4a27432ae3366d8e22c6c13c3c4fc, is 11.3MiB in size and contains 7,351 interactions with 1 unique type of association (e.g., interactsWith) between 174 primary taxa (e.g., <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/ece3.10039>) and 171 associated taxa (e.g., Mull, N., Schexnayder, A., Stolt, A., Sironen, T., & Forbes, K. M. (2023). Effects of habitat management on rodent diversity, abundance, and virus infection dynamics. *Ecology and evolution*, 13(4), e10039. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.10039>). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Authors: Beckett Sterner, Nathan Upham, Jordan Sowards.
 “Rodent-Virus Metadata Extraction.” <https://github.com/SternerLab/SternerLab-MammalVirusData/archive/fc6a60fd4257cc88ec5066213a72e6823d6c67d6.zip>
 2026-06-06T17:41:32.870Z hash://md5/dba4a27432ae3366d8e22c6c13c3c4fc

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11
nomer	0.6.5
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 11.3MiB) under review
elton pull SternerLab/SternerLab-MammalVirusData

# generate review notes
elton review SternerLab/SternerLab-MammalVirusData \
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions SternerLab/SternerLab-MammalVirusData \
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names SternerLab/SternerLab-MammalVirusData \
| nomer append col \
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

You can find a copy of the full review script at [check-data.sh](#). See also [GitHub](#) and [Codeberg](#).

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull SternerLab/SternerLab-MammalVirusData`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review SternerLab/SternerLab-MammalVirusData`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions SternerLab/SternerLab-MammalVirusData`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names SternerLab/SternerLab-MammalVirusData`)

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in Appendix A. Review Files.

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named SternerLab/SternerLab-MammalVirusData, has fingerprint hash://md5/dba4a27432ae3366d8e22c6c13c3c4fc, is 11.3MiB in

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

size and contains 7,351 interactions with 1 unique type of association (e.g., interactsWith) between 174 primary taxa (e.g., <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/ece3.10039>) and 171 associated taxa (e.g., Mull, N., Schexnayder, A., Stolt, A., Sironen, T., & Forbes, K. M. (2023). Effects of habitat management on rodent diversity, abundance, and virus infection dynamics. *Ecology and evolution*, 13(4), e10039. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.10039>).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped csv, tsv, geopackage and parquet archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped html page at indexed-interactions.html.gz are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10101820	interactsWith	Grzybek, M., Tolkacz, K., Sironen, T., Mäki, S., Alsarraf, M., Behnke-Borowczyk, J., Biernat, B., Nowicka, J., Vaheri, A., Henttonen, H., Behnke, J. M., & Bajer, A. (2020). Zoonotic Viruses in Three Species of Voles from Poland. <i>Animals</i> : an open access journal from MDPI, 10(10), 1820. https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10101820	Authors: Beckett Sterner, Nathan Upham, Jordan Sowards. “Rodent-Virus Metadata Extraction.” Accessed at https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1E6HLAUoH_ByT8KG3tSLfpc4Tmb7vbidSTNxsKGSyrk/export?format=csv&gid=1031433960#gid=1031433960 on 08 Jun 2026.

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10101820	390/ani10101820	Grzybek, M., Tolkacz, K., Sironen, T., Mäki, S., Alsarraf, M., Behnke- Borowczyk, J., Biernat, B., Nowicka, J., Vaheiri, A., Henttonen, H., Behnke, J. M., & Bajer, A. (2020). Zoonotic Viruses in Three Species of Voles from Poland. <i>Animals</i> : an open access journal from MDPI, 10(10), 1820.	Authors: Beckett Sternner, Nathan Upham, Jordan Sowards. “Rodent-Virus Metadata Extraction.”. Accessed at https://docs.goo gle.com/spreadsh eets/d/1E6HL AUoH_ByT8K G3tSLfpc4Tmb 7vbidSTNxsKG- syrk/export?form at=csv&gid=103 1433960#gid=10 31433960 on 08 Jun 2026.
https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10101820	390/ani10101820	Grzybek, M., Tolkacz, K., Sironen, T., Mäki, S., Alsarraf, M., Behnke- Borowczyk, J., Biernat, B., Nowicka, J., Vaheiri, A., Henttonen, H., Behnke, J. M., & Bajer, A. (2020). Zoonotic Viruses in Three Species of Voles from Poland. <i>Animals</i> : an open access journal from MDPI, 10(10), 1820.	Authors: Beckett Sternner, Nathan Upham, Jordan Sowards. “Rodent-Virus Metadata Extraction.”. Accessed at https://docs.goo gle.com/spreadsh eets/d/1E6HL AUoH_ByT8K G3tSLfpc4Tmb 7vbidSTNxsKG- syrk/export?form at=csv&gid=103 1433960#gid=10 31433960 on 08 Jun 2026.

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10101820	interactsWith	Grzybek, M., Tolkacz, K., Sironen, T., Mäki, S., Alsarraf, M., Behnke- Borowczyk, J., Biernat, B., Nowicka, J., Vaheri, A., Henttonen, H., Behnke, J. M., & Bajer, A. (2020). Zoonotic Viruses in Three Species of Voles from Poland. <i>Animals</i> : an open access journal from MDPI, 10(10), 1820. https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10101820	Authors: Beckett Sternner, Nathan Upham, Jordan Sowards. “Rodent-Virus Metadata Extraction.”. Accessed at https://docs.goo gle.com/spreadsh eets/d/1E6HL AUoH_ByT8K G3tSLfpc4Tmb 7vbidSTNxsKG- syrk/export?form at=csv&gid=103 1433960#gid=10 31433960 on 08 Jun 2026.

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
interactsWith	7351

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/ece3.10039	1027
https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11034-015-0909-5	719
https://www.ajtmh.org/view/journals/tjtmh/54/6/article-p570.xml	214
https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/114691809/	189
https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0166093408001699?via%3Dihub	196

sourceTaxonName	count
https://www.liebertpub.com/doi/10.1089/1551-2012.1073	165
https://journals.asm.org/doi/10.1128/jvi.10098-21	160
https://www.liebertpub.com/doi/10.1089/1551-2017.2108	162
https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.1974.23.1159	159
https://academic.oup.com/jid/article-abstract/169/6/1271/913145?redirectedFrom=fulltext	156
https://www.liebertpub.com/doi/10.1089/1551-2009.0206	155
https://esajournals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1890/08-2308.1	147
https://www.ajtmh.org/view/journals/tm/113/41/2/article-p230.xml	141
https://journals.plos.org/plospathogens/article?id=10.1371/journal.ppat.1003438	102
https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/13870586/	86
https://www.ajtmh.org/view/journals/tm/86/73/6/article-p1043.xml	86
https://meridian.allenpress.com/jwd/article/84/11/2/195/118006/SEROLOGIC-EVIDENCE-OF-VENEZUELAN-EQUINE	84
https://academic.oup.com/ilarjournal/article/58/3/401/4959778	82
https://meridian.allenpress.com/jwd/article/80/41/1/1/123510/EPIZOOTIOLOGY-OF-SIN-NOMBRE-AND-EL-MORO-CANYON	80

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Mull, N., Schexnayder, A., Stolt, A., Sironen, T., & Forbes, K. M. (2023). Effects of habitat management on rodent diversity, abundance, and virus infection dynamics. <i>Ecology and evolution</i> , 13(4), e10039. https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.10039	1847
Stritch, C., Naulty, F., Zintl, A. et al. Squirrelpox virus reservoir expansion on the east coast of Ireland. <i>Eur J Wildl Res</i> 61, 483–486 (2015). https://doi.org/10.1007/s10344-015-0909-5	319

targetTaxonName	count
Kosoy, M. Y., Elliott, L. H., Ksiazek, T. G., Fulhorst, C. F., Rollin, P. E., Childs, J. E., Mills, J. N., Maupin, G. O., & Peters, C. J. (1996). Prevalence of antibodies to arenaviruses in rodents from the southern and western United States: evidence for an arenavirus associated with the genus <i>Neotoma</i> . <i>The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene</i> , 54(6), 570–576. https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.1996.54.570	214
Mantooth, S. J., Milazzo, M. L., Bradley, R. D., Hice, C. L., Ceballos, G., Tesh, R. B., & Fulhorst, C. F. (2001). Geographical distribution of rodent-associated hantaviruses in Texas. <i>Journal of vector ecology : journal of the Society for Vector Ecology</i> , 26(1), 7–14.	199
Bego, M. G., Bawiec, D., Dandge, D., Martino, B., Dearing, D., Wilson, E., & St Jeor, S. (2008). Development of an ELISA to detect Sin Nombre virus-specific IgM from deer mice (<i>Peromyscus maniculatus</i>). <i>Journal of virological methods</i> , 151(2), 204–210. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jviromet.2008.05.008	196
Childs, J. E., Ksiazek, T. G., Spiropoulou, C. F., Krebs, J. W., Morzunov, S., Maupin, G. O., Gage, K. L., Rollin, P. E., Sarisky, J., & Enscore, R. E. (1994). Serologic and genetic identification of <i>Peromyscus maniculatus</i> as the primary rodent reservoir for a new hantavirus in the southwestern United States. <i>The Journal of infectious diseases</i> , 169(6), 1271–1280. https://doi.org/10.1093/infdis/169.6.1271	175

targetTaxonName	count
Milazzo, M. L., Amman, B. R., Cajimat, M. N., Méndez-Harclerode, F. M., Suchecki, J. R., Hanson, J. D., Haynie, M. L., Baxter, B. D., Milazzo, C., Jr, Carroll, S. A., Carroll, D. S., Ruthven, D. C., 3rd, Bradley, R. D., & Fulhorst, C. F. (2013). Ecology of Catarina virus (family Arenaviridae) in southern Texas, 2001-2004. Vector borne and zoonotic diseases (Larchmont, N.Y.), 13(1), 50–59. https://doi.org/10.1089/vbz.2012.1073	165
Larsen, B. B., Gryseels, S., Otto, H. W., & Worobey, M. (2022). Evolution and Diversity of Bat and Rodent Paramyxoviruses from North America. Journal of virology, 96(3), e0109821. https://doi.org/10.1128/JVI.01098-21	163
Milazzo, M. L., Cajimat, M. N. B., Richter, M. H., Bradley, R. D., & Fulhorst, C. F. (2017). Muleshoe Virus and Other Hantaviruses Associated with Neotomine or Sigmodontine Rodents in Texas. Vector borne and zoonotic diseases (Larchmont, N.Y.), 17(10), 720–729. https://doi.org/10.1089/vbz.2017.2108	162
Bigler, W. J., Lewis, A. L., & Wellings, F. M. (1974). Experimental infection of the cotton mouse (<i>Peromyscus gossypinus</i>) with Venezuelan equine encephalomyelitis virus. The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene, 23(6), 1185–1188. https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.1974.23.1185	159

targetTaxonName	count
Milazzo, M. L., Barragán-Gomez, A., Hanson, J. D., Estrada-Franco, J. G., Arellano, E., González-Cózatl, F. X., Fernández-Salas, I., Ramirez-Aguilar, F., Rogers, D. S., Bradley, R. D., & Fulhorst, C. F. (2010). Antibodies to Tacaribe serocomplex viruses (family Arenaviridae, genus Arenavirus) in cricetid rodents from New Mexico, Texas, and Mexico. <i>Vector borne and zoonotic diseases</i> (Larchmont, N.Y.), 10(6), 629–637. https://doi.org/10.1089/vbz.2009.0206	155
Previtali, M.A., Lehmer, E.M., Pearce-Duvet, J.M.C., Jones, J.D., Clay, C.A., Wood, B.A., Ely, P.W., Lavery, S.M. and Dearing, M.D. (2010), Roles of human disturbance, precipitation, and a pathogen on the survival and reproductive probabilities of deer mice. <i>Ecology</i> , 91: 582-592. https://doi.org/10.1890/08-2308.1	127
Korch, G. W., Childs, J. E., Glass, G. E., Rossi, C. A., & LeDuc, J. W. (1989). Serologic evidence of hantaviral infections within small mammal communities of Baltimore, Maryland: spatial and temporal patterns and host range. <i>The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene</i> , 41(2), 230–240. https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.1989.41.230	113

targetTaxonName	count
Drexler, J. F., Corman, V. M., Müller, M. A., Lukashev, A. N., Gmyl, A., Coutard, B., Adam, A., Ritz, D., Leijten, L. M., van Riel, D., Kallies, R., Klose, S. M., Gloza-Rausch, F., Binger, T., Annan, A., Adu-Sarkodie, Y., Oppong, S., Bourgarel, M., Rupp, D., Hoffmann, B., ... Drosten, C. (2013). Evidence for novel hepaciviruses in rodents. PLoS pathogens, 9(6), e1003438. https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.ppat.1003438	102
M. Pejcoch et al., “[Prevalence of hantavirus infection in small mammals in the South Moravian Region],” Ceskoslovenska Epidemiologie, Mikrobiologie, Imunologie 41, no. 2 (June 1992): 92–100.	86
MCINTYRE, N. E., CHU, Y., OWEN, R. D., ABUZEINEH, A., DE LA SANCHA, N., DICK, C. W., HOLSOMBACK, T., NISBETT, R. A., & JONSSON, C. (2005). A LONGITUDINAL STUDY OF BAYOU VIRUS, HOSTS, AND HABITAT. The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene Am J Trop Med Hyg, 73(6), 1043-1049. Retrieved Mar 1, 2025, from https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.2005.73.1043	86
Smart, D. L., & Trainer, D. O. (1975). Serologic evidence of Venezuelan equine encephalitis in some wild and domestic populations of southern Texas. Journal of wildlife diseases, 11(2), 195–200. https://doi.org/10.7589/0090-3558-11.2.195	84

targetTaxonName	count
Matthew T Milholland, Iván Castro-Arellano, Elizabeth Arellano, Elizabeth Nava-García, Guadalupe Rangel-Altamirano, Francisco X Gonzalez-Cozatl, Gerardo Suzán, Tony Schountz, Shiara González-Padrón, Ana Viguera, André V Rubio, Troy J Maikis, Bradford J Westrich, Jose A Martinez, Maria D Esteve-Gassent, Madison Torres, Erick R Rodriguez-Ruiz, Dittmar Hahn, Thomas E Lacher, Species Identity Supersedes the Dilution Effect Concerning Hantavirus Prevalence at Sites across Texas and México, ILAR Journal, Volume 58, Issue 3, 2017, Pages 401–412, https://doi.org/10.1093/ilar/ily001	82
Calisher, C. H., Root, J. J., Mills, J. N., Rowe, J. E., Reeder, S. A., Jentes, E. S., Wagoner, K., & Beaty, B. J. (2005). Epizootiology of Sin Nombre and El Moro Canyon hantaviruses, southeastern Colorado, 1995-2000. Journal of wildlife diseases, 41(1), 1–11. https://doi.org/10.7589/0090-3558-41.1.1	80

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/ece3.10039	integrated	Schexnayder, A., Stolt, A., Sironen, T., & Forbes, K. M. (2023). Effects of habitat management on rodent diversity, abundance, and virus infection dynamics. Ecology and evolution, 13(4), e10039. https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.10039	1847
https://link.springer.com/outs/with/10.1007/s10344-015-0909-5	integrated	Naulty, F., Zintl, A. et al. Squirrelpox virus reservoir expansion on the east coast of Ireland. Eur J Wildl Res 61, 483–486 (2015). https://doi.org/10.1007/s10344-015-0909-5	319

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
https://www.ajtmh.org/ajtmh/journals/tropical/article-p570.xml	tro	Elliott, L. H., Ksiazek, T. G., Fulhorst, C. F., Rollin, P. E., Childs, J. E., Mills, J. N., Maupin, G. O., & Peters, C. J. (1996). Prevalence of antibodies to arenaviruses in rodents from the southern and western United States: evidence for an arenavirus associated with the genus Neotoma. The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene, 54(6), 570-576. https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.1996.54.570	214

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/11469186/	Interacts With	<p>Antooth, S. J., Milazzo, M. L., Bradley, R. D., Hice, C. L., Ceballos, G., Tesh, R. B., & Fulhorst, C. F. (2001). Geographical distribution of rodent-associated hantaviruses in Texas. <i>Journal of vector ecology :</i> <i>journal of the Society for Vector Ecology,</i> 26(1), 7–14.</p>	199
https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0166093408001699?via%3Dihub	Interacts With	<p>Bawiec, D., Dandge, D., Martino, B., Dearing, D., Wilson, E., & St Jeor, S. (2008). Development of an ELISA to detect Sin Nombre virus-specific IgM from deer mice (<i>Peromyscus maniculatus</i>). <i>Journal of virological methods,</i> 151(2), 204–210. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jviromet.2008.05.008</p>	093

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	Name	targetTaxonName	count
https://www.liebertpub.com/doi/10.1089/vbz.2012.1073	interactsWith	Milazzo, C. F.	10.1089/vbz.2012.1073	165
		Amman, B. R., Cajimat, M. N., Méndez- Harclerode, F. M., Suchecki, J. R., Hanson, J. D., Haynie, M. L., Baxter, B. D., Milazzo, C., Jr, Carroll, S. A., Carroll, D. S., Ruthven, D. C., 3rd, Bradley, R. D., & Fulhorst, C. F. (2013). Ecology of Catarina virus (family Arenaviridae) in southern Texas, 2001-2004. Vector borne and zoonotic diseases (Larchmont, N.Y.), 13(1), 50-59. https://doi.org/10.1089/vbz.2012.1073		
https://journals.asmi.org/doi/10.1128/jvi.01098-21	interactsWith	Chen, B. B., Gryseels, S., Otto, H. W., & Worobey, M. (2022). Evolution and Diversity of Bat and Rodent Paramyxoviruses from North America. Journal of virology, 96(3), e0109821. https://doi.org/10.1128/JVI.01098-21	10.1128/jvi.01098-21	163

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
https://www.liebertpub.com/doi/10.1089/vbz.2017.2108	With	Cajimat, M. N. B., Richter, M. H., Bradley, R. D., & Fulhorst, C. F. (2017). Muleshoe Virus and Other Hantaviruses Associated with Neotomine or Sigmodontine Rodents in Texas. Vector borne and zoonotic diseases (Larchmont, N.Y.), 17(10), 720–729. https://doi.org/10.1089/vbz.2017.2108	162
https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.1974.23.1185	With	Bigler, W. J., Lewis, A. L., & Wellings, F. M. (1974). Experimental infection of the cotton mouse (Peromyscus gossypinus) with Venezuelan equine encephalomyelitis virus. The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene, 23(6), 1185–1188. https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.1974.23.1185	159

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
https://academic.oup.com/infdis/advance-article-abstract/doi/10.1093/infdis/169.6.1271/913145?redirectedFromFullText	Interaction	Childs, J. E., Kozak, L. E., Spiropoulou, C. F., Krebs, J. W., Morzunov, S., Maupin, G. O., Gage, K. L., Rollin, P. E., Sarisky, J., & Enscore, R. E. (1994). Serologic and genetic identification of Peromyscus maniculatus as the primary rodent reservoir for a new hantavirus in the southwestern United States. The Journal of infectious diseases, 169(6), 1271–1280. https://doi.org/10.1093/infdis/169.6.1271	156

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
https://www.liebertpub.com/doi/10.1089/vbz.2009.0206	interacts with	<p>Barragán-Gomez, A., Hanson, J. D., Estrada-Franco, J. G., Arellano, E., González-Cózatl, F. X., Fernández-Salas, I., Ramirez-Aguilar, F., Rogers, D. S., Bradley, R. D., & Fulhorst, C. F. (2010). Antibodies to Tacaribe serocomplex viruses (family Arenaviridae, genus Arenavirus) in cricetid rodents from New Mexico, Texas, and Mexico. Vector borne and zoonotic diseases (Larchmont, N.Y.), 10(6), 629–637.</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1089/vbz.2009.0206</p>	155

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
https://esajournals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1890/08-2308.1	intraspecific	Lehmer, E.M., Pearce-Duvet, J.M.C., Jones, J.D., Clay, C.A., Wood, B.A., Ely, P.W., Lavery, S.M. and Dearing, M.D. (2010), Roles of human disturbance, precipitation, and a pathogen on the survival and reproductive probabilities of deer mice. Ecology, 91: 582-592. https://doi.org/10.1890/08-2308.1	127

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
https://www.ajtmh.org/ajtmh/journals/tropical/article-p230.xml	With	Childs, J. E., Glass, G. E., Rossi, C. A., & LeDuc, J. W. (1989). Serologic evidence of hantaviral infections within small mammal communities of Baltimore, Maryland: spatial and temporal patterns and host range. The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene, 41(2), 230–240. https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.1989.41.230	113

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
https://journals.plos.org/plosPathogens/article?id=10.1371/journal.ppat.1003438	int	Corman, V. M., Müller, M. A., Lukashev, A. N., Gmyl, A., Coutard, B., Adam, A., Ritz, D., Leijten, L. M., van Riel, D., Kallies, R., Klose, S. M., Gloza-Rausch, F., Binger, T., Annan, A., Adu-Sarkodie, Y., Oppong, S., Bourgarel, M., Rupp, D., Hoffmann, B., ... Drosten, C. (2013). Evidence for novel hepaciviruses in rodents. PLoS pathogens, 9(6), e1003438. https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.ppat.1003438	86
https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1387051/	int	Pejcoch et al., “[Prevalence of hantavirus infection in small mammals in the South Moravian Region],” Ceskoslovenska Epidemiologie, Mikrobiologie, Imunologie 41, no. 2 (June 1992): 92–100.	86

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
https://academic.oup.com/ilar/journal/advance-article-abstract/doi/10.1093/ilar/ily001/4959828		Milholland, Iván Castro-Arellano, Elizabeth Arellano, Elizabeth Nava-García, Guadalupe Rangel- Altamirano, Francisco X Gonzalez-Cozatl, Gerardo Suzán, Tony Schountz, Shiara González-Padrón, Ana Viguera, André V Rubio, Troy J Maikis, Bradford J Westrich, Jose A Martinez, Maria D Esteve-Gassent, Madison Torres, Erick R Rodriguez-Ruiz, Dittmar Hahn, Thomas E Lacher, Species Identity Supersedes the Dilution Effect Concerning Hantavirus Prevalence at Sites across Texas and México, ILAR Journal, Volume 58, Issue 3, 2017, Pages 401–412, https://doi.org/10.1093/ilar/ily001	828

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
https://meridian.allenpress.com/wild/article/doi/10.7589/0090-3558-41.1.1		Epizootiology of Sin Nombre and El Moro Canyon hantaviruses, southeastern Colorado, 1995-2000. Journal of wildlife diseases, 41(1), 1-11. https://doi.org/10.7589/0090-3558-41.1.1	1

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life [download svg](#)

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

You can download the indexed dataset under review at [indexed-interactions.csv.gz](#). A tab-separated file can be found at [indexed-interactions.tsv.gz](#)

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer (McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration indexed-interactions.map :

```
MAP
  SIZE 1600 800
  EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
  PROJECTION
    "init=epsg:4326"
  END
  LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
    NAME "modis_nasa"
    TYPE RASTER
    OFFSITE 0 0 0
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE WMS
    CONNECTION "https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov/wms/epsg4326/best/wms.cgi?"

  METADATA
    "wms_srs" "EPSG:4326"
    "wms_name" "OSM_Land_Water_Map"
    "wms_server_version" "1.1.1"
    "wms_format" "image/jpeg"
  END
  CLASS
    STYLE
      COLOR 232 232 232
      OUTLINECOLOR 32 32 32
    END
  END
  LAYER
    NAME "indexed-interactions"
    TYPE POLYGON
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE OGR
    CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
    DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
    CLASS
      STYLE
        COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
        DATARANGE NULL NULL
        RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
```

```

        OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
      END
    END
  END
END

```

Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at indexed-interactions.gpkg for point data and indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Abbott	NONE	col	Abbott

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Amman B R	NONE	col	Amman B R
Manangan A P			Manangan A P
Flietstra T D			Flietstra T D
Calisher C H			Calisher C H
Carroll D S			Carroll D S
Wagoner K D			Wagoner K D
Mills J N			Mills J N
Association between movement Sin Nombre virus Bunyaviridae Hantavirus infection North American deermice Peromyscus maniculatus Colorado Journal wildlife diseases https doi org			Association between movement Sin Nombre virus Bunyaviridae Hantavirus infection North American deermice Peromyscus maniculatus Colorado Journal wildlife diseases https doi org
Andre	NONE	col	Andre
Bagamian	NONE	col	Bagamian

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	220
col	subgenus	1
discoverlife	NA	222
gbif	NA	219
gbif	genus	2
itis	NA	221
mdd	NA	221
ncbi	NA	222
pbdb	NA	221
tpt	NA	221
wfo	NA	221
worms	NA	221

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	NONE	342
col	SYNONYM_OF	1
discoverlife	NONE	344
gbif	NONE	341
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	1
itis	NONE	343
mdd	NONE	343
ncbi	NONE	344
pbdb	NONE	343
tpt	NONE	343
wfo	NONE	343
worms	NONE	343

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

catalog name	alignment results
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-08T06:20:54Z	note	found [40] columns, but only [23] columns are defined: ignoring remaining undefined columns.
2026-06-08T06:20:54Z	note	invalid date string [R001-Grzybek2020]
2026-06-08T06:20:54Z	note	invalid date string [R001-Grzybek2020]
2026-06-08T06:20:54Z	note	found [40] columns, but only [23] columns are defined: ignoring remaining undefined columns.

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 12: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
found [40] columns, but only [23] columns are defined: ignoring remaining undefined columns.	16386
source taxon name missing	9035
invalid date string [R917-Mull2023]	3694
invalid date string [R891-Davis1974]	638

reviewComment	count
---------------	-------

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-08) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: “Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike.”

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)

filename	description
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

References

- Elliott, Michael, Jorrit Poelen, Icaro Alzuru, Emilio Berti, and partha04patel. 2025. “Bio-Guoda/Preston: 0.10.5.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14662206>.
- ICZN. 1999. “International Code of Zoological Nomenclature.” The International Trust for Zoological Nomenclature, London, UK. <https://www.iczn.org/the-code/the-code-online/>.
- Kuhn, Tobias, and Michel Dumontier. 2014. “Trusty URIs: Verifiable, Immutable, and Permanent Digital Artifacts for Linked Data.” In *The Semantic Web: Trends and Challenges*, edited by Valentina Presutti, Claudia d’Amato, Fabien Gandon, Mathieu d’Aquin, Steffen Staab, and Anna Tordai, 395–410. Cham: Springer International Publishing.

- Kuhn, Tobias, Jorrit Poelen, and Katrin Leinweber. 2025. “Globalbioticinteractions/Elton: 0.15.1.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14927734>.
- McKenna, Jeff, Steve Lime, Thomas Bonfort, Jérôme Boué, Howard Butler, Seth Girvin, Tom Kralidis, et al. 2025. “MapServer.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17807263>.
- Poelen, Jorrit H. (ed.). 2024. “Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources Hash://Sha256/ B60c0d25a16ae77b24305782017b1a270b79b5d1746f832650 F2027ba536e276 Hash://Md5/17f1363a277ee0e4ecaf1b91c665e47e.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12695629>.
- Poelen, Jorrit H., James D. Simons, and Chris J. Mungall. 2014. “Global Biotic Interactions: An Open Infrastructure to Share and Analyze Species-Interaction Datasets.” *Ecological Informatics* 24 (November): 148–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2014.08.005>.
- Poelen, Jorrit, Katja Seltmann, and Daniel Mietchen. 2024. “Globalbioticinteractions/Globinizer: 0.4.0.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10647565>.
- Salim, José Augusto, and Jorrit Poelen. 2025. “Globalbioticinteractions/Nomer: 0.5.15.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14893840>.
- Trekels, Maarten, Debora Pignatari Drucker, José Augusto Salim, Jeff Ollerton, Jorrit Poelen, Filipi Miranda Soares, Max Rünzel, Muo Kasina, Quentin Groom, and Mariano Devoto. 2023. “WorldFAIR Project (D10.1) Agriculture-related pollinator data standards use cases report.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8176978>.
- Wilkinson, Mark D., Michel Dumontier, IJsbrand Jan Aalbersberg, Gabrielle Appleton, Myles Axton, Arie Baak, Niklas Blomberg, et al. 2016. “The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship.” *Scientific Data* 3 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.